

DEVELOPMENT OF AN ANN MODEL FOR DOWNSCALING

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Downscaling, the process of reducing the spatial resolution of an image, is a fundamental task in image processing with applications ranging from multimedia compression to real-time graphics rendering. In this paper, we present the development of an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) tailored specifically for downscaling an input image from an 8x8 resolution to a 2x2 resolution.

Keywords: ANN; downscaling; neurons; activation function.

Introduction

Image downscaling is an important step in different image processing applications, such as image compression, image transmission, and multi-scale representation [1-3]. In the past, downscaling was done mostly through filtering techniques, which could cause the loss of information or blurring. However, new AI-based methods have been developed for image downscaling, which are much more powerful. These methods have the potential to learn complex relationships between input and output images and achieve superior performance [4-6].

Development of an ANN model for downscaling

This section of the paper proposes to implement Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) for image downscaling tasks [7-8]. Image downscaling, the process of reducing image resolution while preserving important visual features, is a crucial component in various image processing applications.

Fig. 1. ANN model for 8x8 to 2x2 downscaling

The detailed view of the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model for downscaling is illustrated in Figure 1.

Neural networks utilize activation functions to convert the sum of weighted input from a node into its output or activation. There are several types of activation functions used in neural networks, and the ANN-based model for downscaling uses the sigmoid activation function.

A sigmoid function is a type of mathematical function that has an "S"-shaped curve. The sigmoid activation function has a mathematical form of $\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{(1+e^{-x})}$ which is shown in Figure 2. It takes a real value and compresses it in the range from 0 to 1. In particular, large negative numbers are equal to 0 and large positive numbers are equal to 1. The sigmoid function is often used in the output layer of binary classification, where the result is either 0 or 1. This is because the value for the sigmoid function lies between 0 and 1, making it easy to predict a result of 1 if the value is greater than 0.5, and 0 otherwise. The sigmoid function is commonly used because it represents "the rate at which a neuron shoots" from total non-shooting (0) to fully saturated shooting at the predicted maximum frequency (1).

Fig. 2. Sigmoid activation function [9]

The proposed model has 64 inputs and 4 outputs. The proposed model consists of two hidden layers (see Figure 1). These two hidden layers are based on the Sigmoid activation function. The first hidden layer consists of 32 neurons. The second hidden layer consists of 8 neurons.

$$f_{act1} = f_{act2} = f_{act3} = \sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}} \quad (1)$$

$$y_n = f_{act3}([\sum_{m=1}^8 out_{3,m} \cdot w_{3,m,n}] + b_{3,n}) \quad (2)$$

$$y_n = f_{act3}([\sum_{m=1}^8 f_{act2}([\sum_{k=1}^{32} out_{2,k} \cdot w_{2,k,m}] + b_{2,m}) \cdot w_{3,m,n}] + b_{3,n}) \quad (3)$$

$$y_n = f_{act3}([\sum_{m=1}^8 f_{act2}([\sum_{k=1}^{32} f_{act1}([\sum_{j=1}^{64} x_j \cdot w_{1,j,k}] + b_{1,k}) \cdot w_{2,k,m}] + b_{2,m}) \cdot w_{3,m,n}] + b_{3,n}) \quad (4)$$

$$y_n = \left[1 + e^{-\left(\sum_{m=1}^8 \frac{w_{3,m,n}}{1 + e^{-\left(\sum_{k=1}^{32} \frac{w_{2,k,m}}{1 + e^{-\left(\sum_{j=1}^{64} x_j \cdot w_{1,j,k} + b_k \right)}} + b_m \right)}} + b_n \right)} \right]^{-1} \quad (4)$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has presented a focused investigation into the development and application of an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model specifically tailored for the task of downscaling images from 8x8 to 2x2 resolution.

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